

**BORROWED WORDS IN THE SPHERE OF FOOD ADVERTISEMENT
BASED ON THE INTERNET SOURCES**

Mamadaliyeva A. M.

TerSU 2 course master

E. M. Davlyatova

Scientific supervisor

PhD

Abstract: The article is devoted to the analysis of the borrowed words in the sphere of food advertisement. The aforementioned idea has become frequent in the recipient languages - Uzbek and Russian - and has become acclimated to them. The aim of the article is in the determination and diagnosis borrowed words in food advertisement and describe linguo-cultural features of such lexemes. The object of the examined issue is borrowed words based on internet sites. The analysis illustrates the existence of such terminology as “borrowed lexemes”, “Anglicisms”, “recipient language”, “source language”. There are different factors which influence the process of penetration and fixing of borrowings from the source language to the recipient language. We used descriptive and structural methods to analyze examples of borrowed words used in advertisements found in the internet.

Key words: advertisement, borrowed words, recipient language, intercultural communication.

The actuality of the theme of our article is determined by the increasing importance of advertising, in particular food advertising in the life of modern society as one of the types of mass communication, as well as the globalization of world economic, political and cultural processes. Moreover, this article focuses on the analysis of borrowed lexemes in the sphere of food advertisement, as it displays cultural exchange. This issue attracts linguists’ attention, as the meanings of many words are not examined and so they are not used correctly. The systematization of

borrowed words can contribute to the linguistics as each category can be examined separately. Consequently, clear discover of the meaning of borrowed words can make a great use not only for linguists but also for those who deal with advertising.

Foreign scientists and Russian ones are extremely interested in this matter and have already done research on it. The works of such scientists as E. Hall, L. Samovar, R. Porter, I.I. Haleyeva, S.G. Terminasova, O.A. Leontovich are of great significance. Such linguists as Clow and Baak examined the functions of advertisement and highlighted two main ones, namely the promotion of awareness of the brand, informing and persuading people¹.

Advertisement has become an inevitable part of the modern world. People run into it everywhere and due to this fact linguists are interested in this issue. However, before investigating it let us clarify the concept of advertisement. At the beginning of the XIX century the word “advertisement” began to be widely used in the English language, but this simply meant “a message about something” in the XIV-XV centuries in the Oxford dictionary. Roman languages such as French, Italian, Spanish also had the same concept in their languages (“publicite” – french, “publicidad” – spanish, “pubblicita” – italian) which emphasized the mass nature of the advertising addressee. Advertisement was developing with trade and the integration of countries led not only to the goods exchange but also to the language exchange. Many words came from one language (source language) and firmly stuck into another (recipient language). Thus, we came to the point of this article – borrowed words.

The main function of advertising is informational and communicative function, as advertising has always been used primarily, as a means of communication between the advertiser and the target audience. The communicative function is also typical of social advertising, which does not inform the audience about a particular brand, but accentuates certain social issues, causes, or the necessity to donate and participate in charities².

¹ Clow K.E. &Baak D. Integrated Advertising, Promotion, and Marketing Communication 2012, p. 230

² Clow K.E. &Baak D. Integrated Advertising, Promotion, and Marketing Communication 2012, p.144

The distinct feature of modern advertisement is usage of borrowed words in order to attract the attention of society. At the turn of the millennium, there was a massive spread of foreign-language borrowings in all types of mass communication and, first of all, in advertising discourse, and advertising served, perhaps, as one of the main sources of Anglicisms in the Russian language. Let us determine the notion of borrowings. A large encyclopedic dictionary gives the following definition of the term borrowing – “it is the transition of elements of one language to another as a result of the interaction of languages or the elements themselves transferred from one language to another. Borrowing can be oral (reproduces the general phonetic appearance of the word) or written, book (when transliteration of the word is performed)”. Thus, borrowed lexemes are inevitable process of communication and cultural exchange. It cannot be also denied that this process has done a positive impact on the issue of advertisement itself. The famous Italian linguist Maurizio Dardano noted that the main task of the EEC language policy is to strengthen ties between the peoples inhabiting Europe. Citizens residing in the European Union must speak at least two languages. As a result, the mutual influence of languages on each other becomes inevitable³. Many researchers pointed that the examination of the language of food advertisement and food discourse as a whole can help to understand the culture of a particular country or nation⁴. Russian researchers who made a research in this sphere are A.B. Olyanich, N. P. Golovnitskaya, A. Yu. Zemskova, L. R. Ishakova, E. A. Cherednikova, P. P. Burkova⁵. However, there are not so many Uzbek scholars who examined borrowed words, A. E. Khudaykulov, E. M. Davlyatova, D.U. Ashurova, D.U. Khoshimova, M.

³ Dardano M. The influence of English on Italian, 1986. P. 231–252.

⁴ Lévi-Strauss, Claude. [Structural Anthropology](#), 2006

⁵ Hall E.T. Silent language. – New York: Doubleday, 1990. –192p.; Samovar L.A., Porter R. Intercultural communication: a reader. – Belmont; Albany; Bonn, etc.: Wadsworth Publishing Company, 1997. –P.379–391; Халеева И.И. Основы теории обучения пониманию иноязычной речи (подготовка переводчика). – М.: Высшая школа, 1989. – 238 с.; Тер-Минасова С.Г. Язык и межкультурная коммуникация. –М.: Слово/Slovo, 2000. –624с.; Леонтович О.А. Введение в межкультурную коммуникацию. –М.: Гнозис, 2007.– 368 с.

G.Makhkamova, M. D. Dzhusupova, A. E. Mamatova⁶ covered this theme in their researches.

The aim of this article is to present examples based on empirical materials, namely internet sites. On the basis of theoretical material and the examples collected from the internet sources, we classified the following groups of food categories. We consider it important to mention, although, that these categories have sub-categories.

Beverages: mineral water (**Hydrolife, Nestle pure life**, etc.); juices (J7, Bliss, etc.); soft drinks (Pepsi, Coca-cola, etc.). There is a crucial need to highlight that brand names are densely entering people's lives. For instance, the Uzbek brand of drinking water "Hydrolife" entered the lexicon of Uzbek or Russian speakers as they rely on the good quality of this water. "**Чистая от природы!**" says its motto which wins over any person as it promises to be pure and natural. The advertisement of "J7" juice, which hints its consumer to get not only sweet taste, but also maximum of use after drinking it attracts the attention of those who follow a healthy diet. "**Микс пользы и вкуса**" – the word "микс" is a borrowed word in Russian language and here it is not about mixture of fruit, but about mixing great taste and health. The most favourite beverage among youth is soft drink and here we would like to present the advertisement of Pepsi which is full of borrowed words. One of them in Uzbek language and says "**Pepsi ritmida bo'!**"- which means "Be in the rhythm of Pepsi". The author wanted to catch consumers' attention and encourage them to drink this beverage as much as possible in order to be energetic. According to one of the versions of the brand name "**pep**" means cheerfulness of the spirit, and perhaps this motivates people consume this soft drink more than others. As for alcohol, there is an advertisement of Grey Goose vodka which says: "**World's best tasting vodka**". Here we may witness that the word

⁶ Ашурова Д.У. Производное слово в свете коммуникативной теории языка. –Т.: Фаң,1991. – 97 с.; Хошимова Д.У. Лакуны как совокупность слов или словосочетаний, маркированных наличием национально-культурного содержательного компонента // Вопросы филологических наук. – 2004. – №6. –96-98 с.; Махкамова М. Г. Формирование межкультурной компетенции студентов филологического вуза (английский язык): Автореф. дисс... док.пед.наук.– Т., 2011.–47с.; Джусупов М. Д. Социоллингвистика, лингводидактика, методика (взаимосвязь и взаимообусловленность) // Русский язык за рубежом. – 2012. – №1. – .22–28 с.; Маматов А.Э. Нутк маданияти ва тил нормасига оид терминлар ва тушунчалар изохи. –Т.: Вауoz, 2014.

“vodka” has not been changed, but transliterated. It is also one of the ways which is used concerning borrowings.

Porridges: porridges of fast preparation (Дядюшка Бишоп, ФрутоНяня, etc.). Such borrowings which are observed in these names are called “calc” as they literally copy the name of a person or foreign word. In the brand name “Дядюшка Бишоп” there is a name of a person

Porridges for children (Nestle, Nan, etc.)

Sweets: chocolate (Alpen Gold fun max); Lollipops (Chupa chups); pastry (Cheesecake, cobbler, мороженое пломбир, etc.)

Fast food advertisements are full of following borrowed words:

a) burgers and hot-dogs (**чизбургер, буги вуги, марьивановна сет, etc.**). These words are inevitable part of our life as we do not translate them, but use in the original form. For instance, we do not say “a sandwich with cheese” we just use the “cheeseburger” itself. Moreover, frequently the names of the burgers, pizzas or desserts are used instead of this type of food.

b) pizzas (**летнее комбо, маргарита, Bellissimo pizza, etc.**) As we can observe in the examples all the borrowed words are the names of pizza and often people while making an order use this words instead of their translations. This way is more convenient and simplifies the speech. Summer “combo” attracts the attention of consumers as this word means “combination” and was used in military sphere to express a number of successful maneuvers.

c) Crisps (**Lays, Cheers, Cheetos, etc.**) The names of snacks also became common, as an example we can take the borrowed word “lays” which came from the name of their creator Herman W.Lay. Cheers are Britain-Uzbek brand of chips which is presumably means “something delicious”.

d) Corn flakes (**Kosmostars**). This name was given to the children breakfast in order to give an appeal to this product as the theme of space is extremely fascinating for children.

Dairy production is the second category which has many borrowed words that has taken a root in our speech.

Yoghurt (**Actimel, Danone, etc.**) Sometimes not the whole word but prefix is taken to form a word. For instance, “actimel” has prefix “act” which means “active”, so the yoghurt with such name promises to give consumer activeness.

Milk cocktails (**Nesquick**) This product promises to give those who drinks it to be quick as the name is composed from two words “nestle” and “quick”.

In general, borrowings are a good trick in the sphere of advertisement and at the beginning of the XX century researchers started to investigate the reasons of this notion. Semantic scholar M.A.Breiter suggested several reasons of appearing of borrowed words in a particular language.

The absence of a corresponding concept in the cognitive base of the recipient language. In case of food advertisement such words as “**yoghurt**”, “**cheesecake**”, “**soufflé**”, “**pizza**”, etc. deeply came into our lives as there are not these very concepts in our culture and language.

The absence of an appropriate, more precise name in the recipient language. For instance, English word “topping” is widely used among Russian or Uzbek speaking chefs as there is no clear equivalent in these languages.

The expression of a positive or negative meaning that the equivalent unit in the recipient language does not possess. Fast food restaurants often use such borrowings as “combo”, “set”, “express” to show the size of a portion, the speed of delivery or the variety of components.

The Uzbek web-site **zira.uz** presents a diversion of recipes where borrowings present originality of a particular meal. We would like to speculate about an unusual meal for our culture, but common one for American culture – cobbler with ice-cream. Cambridge dictionary gives the following definition for this meal: a dish cooked in the oven that consists of cooked food, usually fruit, with a thick bread-like mixture on top. Although this term has not been spread these days yet, but only a

small circle of specialists are familiar with it, another word is very popular among sweet teeth – “пломбир”. This word is originally a French one meaning “a vanilla ice-cream mixed with candied fruits”. One more meal which became a part of everyday menu is cheesecake. The name of this dessert doesn’t exist in Russian and Uzbek languages, it came from English, but as it is widespread in the menus of many restaurants and bakeries, it densely entered into these two languages.

In conclusion, we want to highlight the idea that penetration of borrowed lexemes is inevitable in our era of internet and technologies. It is essential for the linguists to examine this notion not only because of the linguistic factor but also due to the cultural exchange. These lexemes help people learn more about the culture of a particular society.

References:

1. Clow K.E. & Baak D. Integrated Advertising, Promotion, and Marketing Communication 2012, p. 230, p. 144
2. Dardano M. The influence of English on Italian, 1986. P. 231–252.
3. Lévi-Strauss, Claude. [Structural Anthropology](#), 2006
4. Barun S. Ispolzoaniye anglicizmov v sovremennoy russkoy reklame // Undergraduate thesis // University of Zagreb. 2021
5. Shumakova A.N. THE USE OF ANGLICISMS IN ARTICLES ABOUT GASTRONOMY (based on the present-day French periodicals).
6. Uchenova V.V., Staryh N.V. Istoriya reklamy 2002
7. Collins Dictionary. URL : www.collinsdictionary.com.
8. <https://zira.uz>
9. <http://wikipedia.org>